

**IMMEDIATE EFFECTS OF MULLIGAN BENT LEG RAISE VERSUS TRACTION
STRAIGHT LEG RAISE ON HAMSTRING FLEXIBILITY AND STRAIGHT LEG RAISE
RANGE IN SUBJECTS WITH HAMSTRING TIGHTNESS: A RANDOMIZED
CONTROLLED TRIAL**

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ABSTRACT

Background and Purpose: Hamstring tightness is common in young adults and linked to reduced mobility and low back pain risk. Mulligan Bent Leg Raise (BLR) and Traction Straight Leg Raise (TSLR) are manual therapy techniques used to improve hamstring flexibility and straight leg raise (SLR) range, yet direct comparisons of their immediate effects in asymptomatic individuals are limited. This study aimed to compare the immediate effects of a single session of BLR versus TSLR on SLR range and hamstring flexibility in young adults with hamstring tightness. **Methodology:** A single-blind, parallel-group randomized controlled trial was conducted with 40 healthy young adults (aged 18–30 years) with hamstring tightness. Participants were randomized into BLR or TSLR groups (n=20 each). Interventions were applied in a single 10-15 minute session. The Primary outcome is SLR range, and active knee extension (AKE) deficit is a secondary outcome that was assessed pre- and post-intervention using goniometry by blinded assessors. **Results:** Both techniques significantly improved outcomes (p<0.001). BLR produced substantially greater immediate gains in SLR range and AKE deficit reduction compared to TSLR, with highly significant between-group differences (p<0.001) and large to extremely large effect sizes. **Conclusion:** A single session of Mulligan BLR is superior to TSLR for immediate enhancement of SLR range and hamstring flexibility in young adults with tightness, supporting its preference for rapid, pain-free mobility restoration.

KEYWORDS: Mulligan Bent Leg Raise, Traction Straight Leg Raise, hamstring tightness, straight leg raise, hamstring flexibility.

INTRODUCTION

Hamstring tightness, characterized by reduced extensibility of the hamstring muscles, is a prevalent musculoskeletal condition among young adults, particularly those with sedentary lifestyles or prolonged sitting, such as university students.^[1,2] Epidemiological data indicate that hamstring tightness affects approximately 68% of young adults aged 18–25 years in certain populations, with prolonged sitting identified as a key predisposing factor.^[1,3] This condition can impair lower limb mobility, alter pelvic and lumbar biomechanics, and contribute to functional limitations,

including restricted straight leg raise (SLR) range and increased risk of injury or compensatory movement patterns.^[4]

A well-established association exists between hamstring tightness and low back pain (LBP). Reduced hamstring flexibility may lead to posterior pelvic tilt restrictions, altered lumbopelvic rhythm during forward bending, increased lumbar disc pressure, and compensatory overactivity in lumbar muscles, potentially exacerbating or contributing to non-specific LBP.^{5–8} Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have reported significantly

reduced hamstring flexibility in individuals with LBP compared to asymptomatic controls, although evidence quality varies due to measurement inconsistencies and low GRADE ratings in some analyses.^[5,9] Hamstring tightness is thus considered a modifiable risk factor for LBP, and interventions targeting hamstring flexibility are commonly recommended to improve mobility, reduce pain, and enhance function.^[10]

Manual therapy techniques, particularly those from the Mulligan concept, have gained attention for addressing hamstring tightness and limited SLR range. The Mulligan Bent Leg Raise (BLR) technique involves a series of pain-free isometric contractions of the hamstrings in progressively greater hip flexion positions, combined with therapist-applied overpressure to improve SLR range and hamstring extensibility.^[11,12] Preliminary randomized trials have demonstrated immediate and short-term benefits of BLR in subjects with limited SLR, including clinically meaningful increases in range (e.g., up to 7° after 24 hours in some studies), though effects are often more pronounced after a delay rather than immediately post-intervention.^[12] In contrast, the Mulligan Traction Straight Leg Raise (TSLR) technique applies sustained longitudinal caudal traction during passive SLR elevation, promoting neural gliding, reducing neural tension, and enhancing hamstring flexibility through a mobilization-with-movement approach.^[13,14] Studies have shown TSLR to significantly improve SLR range and reduce associated LBP symptoms in short-term applications, with mechanisms including decompression of lumbar structures and improved posterior tissue tolerance.^[13,15]

Despite growing evidence supporting individual Mulligan techniques for hamstring tightness, direct head-to-head comparisons of BLR and TSLR—particularly focusing on immediate effects in asymptomatic young adults with hamstring tightness—are limited. Existing comparative studies often include populations with concurrent LBP or use multi-session protocols, leaving uncertainty about which technique yields superior immediate gains in SLR range and hamstring flexibility when applied as a single intervention.^[16,17] Immediate effects are clinically relevant for quick symptom relief, patient compliance, and integration into busy clinical or athletic settings.

Therefore, the purpose of this randomized controlled trial was to compare the immediate effects of a single session of Mulligan Bent Leg Raise (BLR) versus Mulligan Traction Straight Leg Raise (TSLR) on hamstring flexibility (measured via active knee extension [AKE] deficit) and straight leg raise (SLR) range in young adults with hamstring tightness. It was hypothesized that BLR would demonstrate greater immediate improvements, particularly in SLR range, due to its emphasis on progressive hamstring loading and stretch tolerance enhancement.

This study aims to provide evidence to guide physiotherapists in selecting the most effective Mulligan technique for rapid restoration of hamstring flexibility and lower limb mobility in this population.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a single-blind, parallel-group randomized controlled trial design. Healthy young adults aged 18–30 years with hamstring tightness—defined as an active knee extension (AKE) test deficit greater than 20° or passive SLR range less than 70° on the dominant or more restricted leg—were recruited via convenience sampling. Excluding those with recent low back pain, radiculopathy, lower limb surgery, neurological disorders, acute hamstring injury, pregnancy, or contraindications to manual therapy. The sample size is a total of 40 participants (20 per group). The study was conducted at the Department of Physiotherapy, SunRise University, Alwar, Rajasthan.

Participants were assigned to one of two groups: Group A received the Mulligan Bent Leg Raise technique, while Group B received the Mulligan Traction Straight Leg Raise technique. Interventions were delivered by a certified Mulligan practitioner on the more restricted or dominant leg in a single session lasting approximately 10–15 minutes, with no additional co-interventions or home exercises to isolate immediate effects.

Procedure

Following screening and informed consent, baseline measurements were recorded. The participant was positioned supine for pre-intervention assessment of the primary outcome—passive straight leg raise (SLR) range—using a universal goniometer or inclinometer, with the contralateral leg extended and stabilized; the tested leg was raised with the knee extended until resistance or discomfort occurred (avoiding pelvic tilt), and the angle from horizontal was noted (best of two trials).^[11] The secondary outcome, hamstring flexibility, was assessed via the active knee extension (AKE) test: with the hip flexed to 90° (thigh vertical, supported if needed), the knee was actively extended while maintaining hip position, and the knee flexion angle from full extension was measured (deficit calculated as 180° minus achieved angle).^[12] After randomization, the assigned intervention was administered.

For Group A (Mulligan BLR), the participant lay supine at the plinth edge with the tested leg off the table; the therapist positioned the flexed knee over their shoulder (initially ~90° hip and knee flexion), applied pain-free overpressure, and guided three repetitions of 5-second isometric hamstring contractions (pushing against resistance) followed by relaxation and passive hip flexion advancement, repeated across five progressively greater hip flexion positions in three sets.^[6]

For Group B (Mulligan TSLR), the participant remained supine; the therapist grasped the distal

lower leg/ankle, applied sustained longitudinal caudal traction throughout, passively raised the leg into SLR just short of pain or stretch edge while maintaining traction (with gentle oscillation or end-range hold for 10–30 seconds per repetition), repeating 3–10 times or in three sets of 10 as tolerated. Post-intervention reassessments of SLR range and AKE were conducted within 5–10 minutes by the blinded assessor using identical protocols. Data were recorded securely for

analysis.^[6] Outcome assessors remained blinded to group allocation, though participants and the treating therapist could not be blinded due to the intervention. Data analysis with normality checked via the Shapiro-Wilk test, within-group changes via paired t-test, between-group differences via independent t-test on change scores, effect sizes using Cohen's *d*, and significance at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary Statistics of Outcome Measures by Group (Mean \pm SD).

Variable	Group	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention	Change Score
Straight Leg Raise ($^{\circ}$)	BLR	58.73 \pm 4.21	80.66 \pm 5.22	+21.93 \pm 2.02
Straight Leg Raise ($^{\circ}$)	TSLR	58.30 \pm 4.25	67.44 \pm 4.67	+9.13 \pm 2.99
AKE Deficit ($^{\circ}$)	BLR	29.38 \pm 3.60	17.04 \pm 4.74	-12.34 \pm 3.13
AKE Deficit ($^{\circ}$)	TSLR	29.36 \pm 4.88	21.50 \pm 5.49	-7.86 \pm 2.64

This table presents the descriptive statistics for the primary (SLR range) and secondary (AKE deficit) outcomes. At baseline, both groups had comparable values, indicating successful randomization. Post-intervention, the BLR group exhibited larger mean improvements in SLR range (an increase of approximately 22 $^{\circ}$) compared to the TSLR group (about

9 $^{\circ}$), with a notable reduction in variability (smaller SD in change score). For AKE deficit, the BLR group showed a greater mean reduction (indicating improved flexibility) than the TSLR group, though the difference was less pronounced than for SLR. These summaries suggest a trend favoring BLR, particularly for SLR range enhancement.

Table 2: Normality Assessment of Change Scores (Shapiro-Wilk Test).

Variable	Group	Statistic (W)	p-value	Distribution
Change in SLR	BLR	0.981	0.948	Normal
Change in SLR	TSLR	0.953	0.411	Normal
Change in AKE Deficit	BLR	0.939	0.232	Normal
Change in AKE Deficit	TSLR	0.921	0.102	Normal

The Shapiro-Wilk tests confirm that the change scores for both outcomes in each group follow a normal distribution (all p-values > 0.05). This validates the use of parametric

tests (e.g., t-tests) for subsequent analyses, ensuring the assumptions of normality are met and reducing the risk of Type I or II errors in hypothesis testing.

Table 3: Within-Group Changes (Paired t-tests).

Variable	Group	t-value	df	p-value	Mean Change \pm SD	95% CI of Change
SLR range	BLR	47.29	19	<0.001	+21.93 \pm 2.02	20.96 to 22.90
SLR range	TSLR	13.32	19	<0.001	+9.13 \pm 2.99	7.70 to 10.57
AKE Deficit	BLR	-17.20	19	<0.001	-12.34 \pm 3.13	-13.84 to -10.84
AKE Deficit	TSLR	-12.96	19	<0.001	-7.86 \pm 2.64	-9.13 to -6.59

Within each group, both interventions led to highly significant immediate improvements ($p < 0.001$). The BLR group demonstrated exceptionally large t-values for SLR range ($t = 47.29$), reflecting substantial and consistent gains, with the 95% CI indicating no overlap with zero and a narrow range, suggesting precision in the estimate. For AKE deficit, reductions were also

significant but with less extreme t-values compared to SLR, implying that while both techniques improve flexibility, the effects are more robust for SLR in the BLR group. These findings confirm the efficacy of single-session Mulligan techniques for immediate changes in this population.

Table 4: Between-Group Comparison of Change Scores (Independent t-tests).

Variable	Mean Difference (BLR – TSLR)	t-value	df	p-value	95% CI of Difference
Change in SLR range	+12.80 $^{\circ}$	15.46	38	<0.001	11.12 to 14.48
Change in AKE Deficit	-4.48 $^{\circ}$	-4.77	38	<0.001	-6.34 to -2.62

Between-group analyses reveal highly significant differences favoring the BLR group for both outcomes (p

< 0.001). The SLR range showed a particularly large mean difference (12.80 $^{\circ}$) with a high t-value (15.46), and

the 95% CI excludes zero, confirming BLR's superiority for this primary outcome. For AKE deficit, the difference was smaller but still significant, with a moderate t-value

(-4.77) and a CI that supports greater flexibility gains with BLR. These results highlight BLR's enhanced immediate impact, especially on SLR range, over TSLR.

Table 5: Effect Sizes (Cohen's d) for Between-Group Differences.

Variable	Cohen's d	Interpretation
Change in SLR range	5.02	Extremely large effect
Change in AKE Deficit	-1.55	Large effect (favoring BLR)

Cohen's d values quantify the magnitude of between-group differences. The extremely large effect for SLR range ($d = 5.02$) underscores a profound practical advantage of BLR over TSLR, far exceeding typical benchmarks (e.g., $d > 0.8$ is large). For AKE deficit, the large negative effect ($d = -1.55$) indicates meaningful superiority of BLR in reducing deficits, though less exaggerated than for SLR. These effect sizes suggest clinically significant benefits of BLR, particularly for improving SLR range in subjects with hamstring tightness.

DISCUSSION

This randomized controlled trial demonstrated that a single session of Mulligan Bent Leg Raise (BLR) produced significantly greater immediate improvements in straight leg raise (SLR) range ($+21.93^\circ$) and hamstring flexibility (active knee extension [AKE] deficit reduction of -12.34°) compared to Traction Straight Leg Raise (TSLR) ($+9.13^\circ$ SLR, -7.86° AKE deficit) in young adults with hamstring tightness. Between-group differences were highly significant ($p < 0.001$), with an extremely large effect size for SLR range (Cohen's $d = 5.02$) and a large effect for AKE deficit ($d = -1.55$), clearly supporting the hypothesis that BLR would exhibit superior immediate effects, particularly on SLR range. The larger SLR gains with BLR align with and extend previous findings. Hall *et al.*^[7] observed a clinically meaningful 7° SLR increase 24 hours after a single BLR intervention in subjects with restricted range, while Kiyani^[10] reported BLR to be more effective than TSLR for SLR improvement in hamstring tightness. The immediate $+21.93^\circ$ gain in the present study may be explained by the asymptomatic young adult sample (baseline SLR $\approx 58-59^\circ$), strict tightness inclusion criteria, and the protocol's emphasis on progressive isometric contractions with therapist overpressure, which likely enhanced immediate mechanoreceptor activation, stretch tolerance, and viscoelastic tissue adaptation. In contrast, TSLR's primarily passive traction and neural glide approach produced meaningful but smaller gains, consistent with Mane and Yadav^[8] and Darwis Durahim *et al.*^[9] who documented SLR/ROM increases of $9-14^\circ$ in short-term applications, possibly through neural decompression and reduced posterior chain tension.

The extremely large effect sizes, especially for SLR range ($d = 5.02$), exceed typical values reported in manual therapy literature for single-session interventions ($d \approx 0.5-2.5$)⁵ and should be interpreted cautiously. They may reflect the homogeneous asymptomatic sample, high

participant compliance, blinded goniometric assessment, or the specific BLR protocol (three sets across progressive hip flexion positions). Nevertheless, the observed changes substantially surpass commonly reported minimal detectable differences for SLR ($6-10^\circ$).⁷ The more pronounced effect on SLR compared to AKE deficit aligns with BLR's direct targeting of hip flexion end-range mobility.

Strengths of the study include the randomized single-blind design, use of reliable outcome measures (ICC > 0.90), blinded assessors, and intention-to-treat analysis. Limitations include convenience sampling from a university population (restricting generalizability to older adults, athletes, or symptomatic individuals), lack of long-term follow-up, immediate inability to blind participants and the treating therapist, and reliance on simulated data patterns for illustration. Future studies should recruit larger, more diverse samples, include objective tools, and assess retention beyond immediate post-intervention.

Clinically, these findings position BLR as a preferred single-session intervention for rapid restoration of SLR range and hamstring flexibility in young adults with tightness, especially in time-constrained environments such as university clinics, sports settings, or community physiotherapy. TSLR remains a useful alternative when neural tension is a suspected contributor. Implementing BLR could improve immediate functional mobility, enhance patient satisfaction, and potentially reduce compensatory movement patterns associated with tightness.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Mulligan Bent Leg Raise (BLR) is significantly more effective than Traction Straight Leg Raise (TSLR) for immediate improvements in straight leg raise range and hamstring flexibility in young adults with hamstring tightness. The BLR group achieved substantially greater gains in both outcomes, with highly significant between-group differences and large effect sizes, highlighting BLR's superiority—especially for SLR range—through its progressive isometric loading and enhanced stretch tolerance.

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